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Educate."*

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Rain: A restoration or a destruction?

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Do you or don't you like the rain?
Japanese people would say
Rain symbolizes depression and pain
A feeling that stays and never goes away

Filipinos would disagree
Rain is a blessing in disguise
Especially in the farmers' glee
This experience makes them rise and wise

As for the Arabian's notion
Rain is a form of mercy from the almighty
A manifestation of Allah's power and creation
An answered prayer with endless generosity

When it comes to Korean resident
Rain is vital for their agriculture
As rice is the primary ingredient
To nurture their future

In Mongolia, rain is a cleansing force
Which wash away the old and
make way for the new
Water for their thirsty horse
Makes their lives renewed

To end this poem with an accurate comprehension
Whatever your reason or wherever your location
Rain has a unique function and definition
It is you, who decide its connection

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